

Research

An Assessment of Carbon Stock in Eucalyptus Forest with Variation in Stand Age in Rawatamai Afforestation Project Area, Jhapa, Nepal

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Abstract: The research was focused to quantify and compare variation of carbon stock (above and below ground) with various age stands in planted living biomass of Eucalyptus forest. Four sample plots were established in each hector for single aged plantation area. Concentric circular plots were established to measure forest biomass. Eucalyptus plants of different stand age up to pole were measured establishing circle of radius 5.64 m. For determining soil carbon content, 3 soil samples (0-10 cm, 11-20 cm and 21-30 cm) up to a depth of 30 cm were collected randomly and made composite mixing soil from each sample plots in same proportion. Collected soil sample were tested in laboratory to determine the carbon content. The data obtained from lab were analyzed with the carbon stock calculation formula proposed by Pukkala (1990) and Walkley (1958). It was carried out to assess and quantify the soil and vegetation carbon stock as well as carbon stock variation in soil and vegetation in Eucalyptus forest with variation in stand age. Random sampling was used for the estimation of above ground and below ground biomass. The biomass carbon content was taken 47% of the dry biomass as followed by Total stem volume was calculated using equation developed by Chave et. al. (2005). Root carbon was calculated as 12.5% of above ground carbon. The average bulk density of Ratuwamai Afforestation Project (RAP) was found to be 1.44 gm./cu.cm. Similarly the average soil organic carbon percent of RAP was found to be 1.19. And the average soil organic carbon percent in 0-10 cm, 11-20 cm & 21-30 cm was 1.61, 1.19 & 0.91 respectively. The total amount of soil organic carbon up to 30 cm depth in RAP was 35.97 t/ha. The carbon stock in Eucalyptus was increased with the increase in stand age. The soil carbon was fluctuated with age as well as with the presence & absence of the vegetation.

Keywords: Forest Biomass, Root Carbon, Bulk density, Soil Organic Carbon, Vegetation

1. Introduction

Carbon stock is the quantity of carbon contained in a "pool", meaning a reservoir or system which has the capacity to accumulate or release carbon. Terrestrial vegetation is an important component of the global carbon cycle, storing over 600 Giga ton of carbon and annually exchanging approximately 10% of that carbon with the atmosphere via photosynthesis and respiration (*Schimel, 2000*). Covering over 4.1 billion hectares, forests contain over 80% of aboveground terrestrial carbon, and relatively minor alterations to carbon storage or cycling in forest ecosystems may have Substantial impact on atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations. Consequently, developing techniques to accurately assess forest carbon over large areas has increasing global relevance.

Global climate change is the serious threat face by the people in 21st century. Global warming will have real threat and consequences of rise in sea level, change in precipitation pattern, increased risk of floods, drought, diseases and decrease in biodiversity. High temperature and erratic rainfall are the major evidence of this (Gautam et al., 2019; Sharma et al., 2019). Forests play an important role in the global carbon balance. As both carbon sources and sinks, they have potential to form an important component in efforts to combat global climate change. Accounting for the carbon within forest ecosystems and changes in carbon stocks resulting from human activities is a necessary first step towards the better representation of forests in climate change policy at regional, national and global scales. Forest carbon stocks and fluxes vary with forest age, and relationships with forest age are often used to estimate fluxes for regional or national carbon inventories. Two methods are commonly used to estimate forest age: observed tree age or time since a known disturbance. Current global circulation models from National Assessment Synthesis Team predict that average annual global surface air temperatures may increase by approximately 2.5⁰ C by the end of this century. Much of the increase in air temperature has been attributed to the increase in atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) over the past 100 years (*NAST, 2000*).

In the global warming issues, carbon absorption by forest ecosystem receives considerable attention now. Forests form both natural and plantation forests, a major component of the carbon reserves in the world's ecosystem and greatly influence the lives of other organism as well as

human societies (*Komiyama et al., 2008*). Global warming is mainly caused by increase in an amount of carbon dioxide (CO₂) which is the major "greenhouse" gases that is contributing the global warming. Carbon emission from deforestation account for an estimated 20 % of global carbon emissions (*IPCC 2007*), second only to that produced by fossil fuel combustion.

Afforestation and reforestation are very prospective forestry project under the clean development mechanism of Kyoto Protocol. Tree growth by CO₂ fixation through photosynthesis process can decrease concentration of CO₂ gases in atmosphere. This is very important provision of the Kyoto Protocol, in which developing countries with tropical rain forest are to be involved in an effort to decrease carbon emission through the development of carbon sink, biodiversity, and sustainable forest management. Estimating carbon sequestration in planted forests is very important activity within global warming issues. Due lack of proper policy and legal framework (*Sapkota et al., 2020*) still people and government of developing country are not still fully convinced.

Nepal signed the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) on June 12, 1992 and ratified it on May 2, 1994 making it effective in the country from July 31, 1994. As a party to the Convention, Nepal is obliged and committed to acting against the earth's climate change and the adverse effects of human activities. It is also a signatory to the Kyoto Protocol and became party to the conference from December 2005. Emission reductions from avoided deforestation have been regarded as a key element of Cost effective future climate change policy (*Anger and Sathaye, 2008*). Therefore, inclusion of avoided deforestation and degradation to reduce Green House Gas (GHG) emissions has been deliberated since the Kyoto Protocol. Reducing emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD) in developing countries is an instrument aimed at reducing deforestation, and providing important opportunity for developing countries to contribute significantly to emission reduction efforts under the international climate regime. In addition, many accompanying benefits, including environmental service from reducing deforestation, could be expected. Advanced remote sensing technologies for forest monitoring are not easily available in Nepal (*Oli and Shrestha, 2008*).

Carbon accumulation in forest and soil eventually reaches a saturation point beyond which additional sequestration is no longer possible. When trees reach maturity or when the organic matter in soil builds back up to original levels before losses occurred. Even after saturation the trees or agriculture practices would need to be sustained to maintain the accumulated carbon and prevent subsequent losses of carbon back to the atmosphere. Carbon sequestration from atmosphere can be advantageous from both environmental and socioeconomic perspectives. The environmental perspective includes the removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere, the improvement of soil quality, and the increase in biodiversity (*Batjes and Sombroek, 1997*); while socioeconomic benefits include increased yields (*Sombroek et al., 1993*) and monetary incomes from potential carbon trading schemes (*McDowell, 2002*). The *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* now is widely adopted as fast growing species by the farmers in Terai and by Ratuwamai Afforestation Project, Kerkha with an objective to produce electricity pole and fuel wood but there is no any reliable biomass table for this species. In addition, the biomass equation is fundamental need of carbon estimation. In this context, different types of equations are used to estimate the biomass by different institutions and research organizations.

2. Rational of the study

There is a worldwide consensus that the climate change is spreading threat in this century. Current knowledge of forest carbon, carbon budgets and ecosystem change process is especially lacking in highly heterogeneous and diverse mountainous regions such as Hindu Khush (HKH) and Nepal as being among the most vulnerable countries to climate change and it is the main concern issue to mitigate climate change for the betterment of the environment. Sustainable forest practices can increase the ability of forest to sequester atmospheric carbon while enhancing other ecosystem services, such as improved soil water quality. Planting new trees and improving forest health through thinning and prescribed burning are some of the ways to increase forest carbon in the long run. Harvesting and regeneration forest can also result in net carbon sequestration in wood products and new forest growth. In context of Nepal, many researchers have assessed the carbon stock. Researches on different Forest management regime and species can be found. A research carried out to examine the effect of biomass burning in the atmospheric carbon dioxide using advanced Earth observation satellite (ADEOS) in 1998 covering all the five physiographic zones of central Nepal showed that the burned fuel wood

biomass had resulted 5.6 million tons of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. On the average more than 300,000 tons per year of carbon dioxide was added in the atmosphere (Amatya et al. 2002). Researches on different forest management regime and species can be found in the literature. However, there is an important information gap on the differential amount of carbon stocking in artificially regenerated (human intervention) *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* forest of Kerkha, Jhapa, Nepal. This research will help in quantifying the variation in carbon stock of different aged *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* forest and other species in the same altitudinal and climatic zone as well as aspect and also very imperatives and useful to forestry sector for planning and policy making by the concern research based organization and also this study will be pioneer work in *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* forest of Kerkha, Jhapa, Nepal. The objective of this research is to assess the soil carbon stock variation in soil and vegetation in Eucalyptus forest with age gradation

3. Methods and Materials

3.1 Study area:

Plantation site of Ratuwamai Afforestation Project, Kerkha situated in Jhapa district of Eastern Development Region of Nepal was selected for this study (Figure 1). The project had executed massive plantation of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*. The temperature of the study area ranges from 20⁰ to 25⁰C and average annual rainfall ranges from 1100 to 3500 mm. The total area of project is 2,713 ha. and out of which plantation area was 2,240 ha, protected Eucalyptus forest 415ha. Sissoo 105 ha and Teak 95 ha. Ratuwamai is the legal production site of Eucalyptus for fuel wood and electric pole in Nepal. The region behind the selection of that area was because of easy to access the data of stand age of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*

Fig.1: Map of the Study Area

3.2 Data collection

a) Sampling Design

Random sampling was used for collecting data for plant biomass. Measurement of tree dbh was done based on the stand age. Based on the stratification nine 1-ha blocks were established; each for single age, categories as

Table 1. Sample plot distribution based on the stand age.

First year	Second year	Third year	Fourth Year	Fifth Year	Sixth Year	Seventh year	Eighth Year	Ninth Year
1-ha	1-ha	1-ha	1-ha	1-ha	1-ha	1-ha	1-ha	1-ha

In each 1 - ha no. of blocks sample plots were plotted estimated using 5% sampling intensity of block area and principle of "proportional allocation of field plots" were used to carry out the sample plot allocation. Five circular sample plots of 100 m² areas were allocated of following size for the measurement of saplings and poles.

Saplings & Poles: - 10m X 10m

Fig. 2: Sample plot design

b) Plant measurement

Diameter at Breast Height (sapling at 15 cm and pole at 1.3m) measurement of Eucalyptus of various stand age was measured using dia. tape (D-tape) and height of each tree was estimated using Abney's level.

(b) Soil Sampling

Soil samples were taken, one from each of the sample plots used for forest inventory considering the stand age. Soil samples were taken from soil profile up to 30 cm depth of 3 different levels (0-10 cm, 11-20cm & 21-30 cm). A core ring sampler (4 cm diameter and 30 cm length) was used for bulk density. Each sample was bagged, labeled and transported to laboratory for further analysis.

Secondary data collection

Secondary data sources included journals, websites and thesis of various individuals and various published reports of government offices such as Ministry of Forests and Soil Conservation (MOFSC), Department of Forest (DoF), Ratuwamai Afforestation Project, Kerkha, Jhapa, department of REED, District forest office(DFo), and other concerning NGO's and INGO's and various other concerned agencies.

3.3 Data Analysis

The collected information was analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative methods using software MS Excel. The result was interpreted using text, tables and figures. The detail of analysis methods is given below:

Above ground tree biomass:

We used equ (i) to calculate the biomass.

$\ln y = a + b \ln x$ (i)

Where y = oven dry wt. in kg (Biomass), x = dbh

Where variable is either dia at breast height at (1.3m) or basal diameter

And a and b are species specific constants.

To calculate above ground biomass, the sum of all individual eucalyptus weights in kg of sample plots of each 1 ha areas. The biomass weight was converted in to $t\ ha^{-1}$. Since the plots areas were part of the whole plantation areas, the biomass stock of each year of 1 ha was found.

Below ground biomass/ Root biomass

It is necessary to calculate the root biomass as roots play as important role in the carbon cycles as they transfer considerable amounts of C to the ground, where it may be stored for a relatively long period of time. The plant uses part of the C in the roots to increase the total tree biomass through photosynthesis.

For study, following relationship was used for estimating the root biomass.

For Eucalyptus species:

Below ground biomass = 12.5% of above ground biomass..... (ii) (Walkley et al., 1958).

Soil carbon and Bulk density Analysis

Soil Organic Carbon (SOC)

The walkey-Black method (Jackson, 1958) was applied to measure the soil organic percent. Total soil carbon was calculated using the formula given below (Chabbara et al., 2002).

$SOC = \text{Organic carbon\%} \times \text{Soil bulk density (gm. /cc)} \times \text{thickness of horizon (cm)}$

Further it was expressed in t/ha.

Bulk density (BD)

Soil core of 4 cm diameter and 30 cm length was used for collecting the bulk density of the soil sample along the soil profile. Soil sample were transported to the laboratory for oven drying and measuring the oven dry weight after drying 24 hrs. at constant temperature of 105⁰C and BD was computed using the following formula.

$$\text{BD (gm. /cc)} = (\text{Oven dry weight of soil})/(\text{Volume of the soil in the core})$$

Net Carbon Content

Total carbon content = above ground organic carbon + root carbon + soil carbon

4. Results and discussion

Soil Organic Carbon Percent & Bulk Density status: Land-dwelling vegetation store more than 600 ton of Carbon and annually (*Schimel, 1995*). In our study, Average soil organic carbon percent was found to be 1.19. The average soil organic carbon percent in 0-10 cm, 11-20cm & 21-30 cm was 1.61, 1.19 & 0.91 respectively. Average bulk density of *Eucalyptus* forest in Ratuwa Mai was 1.44gm/ cm³ and average bulk density of different soil depths, i.e. 0-10 cm, 11-20 cm & 21-30 cm were 1.29gm/ cm³, 1.441gm/cm³ & 1.55gm/ cm³ respectively.

Soil carbon

Fig. 3: Soil carbon in t/ha.

- In the above figure, Soil carbon stock also increases with increase in age stand but there is fluctuation in soil organic carbon among various stand age because of leaf litter collection and other operations like grass cutting and bushes clearing.

Tree biomass status in Ratuwamai Afforestation Project, Kerkha, Jhapa

a) Above and below ground average Carbon stock in *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* (t/ha.)

Fig. 4: Average Carbon stock in *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* in t/ha.

In the figure 2, the average C stock above ground and below ground is 15.49 t/ ha & 1.94 t/ha respectively. The average C stock in *Eucalyptus* of various stand age is 17.42 t/ha.

Above and below ground biomass & Carbon stock in *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* (t/ha.) variation with age.

Fig. 5: Carbon stock in *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* in t/ha.

Below ground and above ground biomass increased with the increase in the stand age. Similarly, the tree (*Eucalyptus*) C stock increased with the increase in the stand age (Fig.3)

5. Conclusions

The carbon stock in the *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* increases with the increase in stand age. Average quantity of the carbon stock in above and below the soil in selected species (*Eucalyptus camaldulensis*) was found to be 15.49 t/ha. & 1.94 t/ha respectively. The amount of average soil organic carbon 0-10 cm was found greater than 11-20 cm & 21-30cm in various stand age. But there is fluctuation in soil organic carbon among various stand age because of leaf litter collection and other operations like grass cutting and bushes clearing. Comparative study about the growth rate of *Eucalyptus* should be studied between mixed and pure plantation area.

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7. Conflict of interest: The author declares no conflict of interest

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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